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1. Executive Summary

This document provides a comprehensive overview of Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) and their critical role in transforming the wireless communication landscape, particularly in the 5G and upcoming 6G standards. It emphasizes the attention that NTNs have received in recent years, motivated by their ability to provide innovative solutions to global connectivity challenges, increase network capacity, and support a wide range of services and applications.

The document first examines the evolution of NTNs, from their conceptual design to their current state of development, detailing the critical standardization efforts conducted by the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP). This standardization activity reflects an ongoing transformation, which is supported by a collaborative effort to effectively integrate NTNs into the global communication ecosystem.

The document then discusses the regulatory and operational challenges associated with the deployment of NTNs. These challenges include spectrum management, interoperability with terrestrial networks, and ensuring global coverage to meet the needs of various applications. Furthermore, the document identifies the opportunities NTNs provide for remote areas where traditional connectivity solutions are impractical or too expensive.

Regarding the standardization initiatives, the document emphasizes the importance of a harmonized approach to ensure that NTNs can be integrated with existing and future terrestrial networks. This involves addressing technical specifications, security concerns, and compatibility issues, which are critical for their successful adoption and implementation. Furthermore, the document presents a detailed state of the art, considering both research literature and ongoing research activities funded by national and European agencies.

A significant portion of this document is devoted to delineating the NTN Technical Requirements, rooted in the ITU-R M.2514-0 specifications. These requirements are meticulously identified to ensure the integration of satellite components with terrestrial networks, thereby fostering service continuity, especially across underserved locales. The document intricately details the technical requisites essential for supporting the 3GPP defined use cases enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB) and massive machine-type communications (mMTC), tailored to satellite interfaces and focus of our study.

Finally, the document presents the requirements for the evaluation of a set of commercial use cases for NTNs. We have selected a direct-to-handset and IoT connectivity use cases, employing a Tradespace methodology to analyze different architectural configurations. The scenarios are meticulously characterized by the critical requirements for a relevant evaluation considering constellation types, payload capacities, and operational metrics, thereby facilitating informed decision-making in satellite constellation design. This comprehensive analysis underscores the potential of NTNs in revolutionizing offshore communications, IoT applications, and beyond.

2. State of the Art Review

2.1. Non-Terrestrial Networks Standardization Initiatives

Initially known as Satellite Communications (SatComs) and aimed at providing service to applications such as TV broadcasting or backhauling, the evolution of non-terrestrial networks has shifted the focus towards the provision of data services with the potential to offer ubiquitous broadband service [1]. It is precisely in this new paradigm that the Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) term was coined within the framework of the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) standardization, thus recognizing the potential of NTNs in enhancing and complementing terrestrial networks.

NTN have been gaining significant attention in the context of wireless communication, particularly in the scope of the 5G and the upcoming 6G technologies. The journey of NTNs, especially in the standardization process by the 3GPP, presents an important evolution from its inception to its current state.

As the 3GPP standards evolved, NTNs began to take shape, starting with Release 15 [2]. This release, while primarily laying down the foundational elements of 5G technology, set the stage for the future integration of NTNs. Among its contributions were the Study Items to analyze the potential of NTN in the context of the well-known service categories, namely enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) and Ultra-Reliable and Low Latency Communications (URLLC). However, the evolution towards 6G will pose new use cases and services beyond the initial eMBB, URLLC and mMTC definition. According to [3], the initial use cases will evolve to 5 use cases with additional and more stringent requirements, that can be summarized/categorized into: eMBB+; URLLC+, mMTC+; Artificial Intelligence (AI); and Sensing, as shown in Figure 1 extracted from [4].

Figure 1. Overview of typical 6G use cases. Figure extracted from [3].

To meet the envisioned requirements and technological challenges, six core technological pillars will define how 6G will be, ranging native AI, networked sensing, extreme connectivity, sustainability, native trustworthiness, and integrated NTN [3]. As for the integrated NTN, the evolution from 5G to 6G is expected to move from the interworking between Terrestrial Networks (TN) and NTN in pre-5G systems, to the integration of TN and NTN in 5G and 5G-Advanced (defined as seamless operation of space-borne and terrestrial segments to provide coverage continuity), and finally the unification of both segments in the future 6G, where both TN and NTN are to be jointly operated and optimized [4].

The real turning point in the development of NTNs came with Release 16 [5]. This was a pivotal moment when NTNs were formally recognized and included within the 3GPP standards. The release significantly expanded the capabilities of the 5G New Radio (NR) to support NTNs, incorporating specific adaptations to cater to the unique requirements of space-based and aerial networks. Key aspects such as beamforming, mobility mechanisms, and synchronization were addressed, tailoring the technology to suit the distinct characteristics of NTNs.

The first works on NTNs in the framework of 3GPP standardization activities were conducted in Releases 15 and 16 as Study Items, being the study phase of NTNs, and setting the basis for the normative phase started in Release 17 and continued in Release 18 and Release 19. The study items in Releases 15 and 16 encompassed both Radio Access Networks (RAN) and Service & System Aspects (SA), and resulted in outcomes included in TR 38.811 [6] and TR 38.821 [7] for RAN, and TS 22.261 [8], TR 22.822 [9], TR 23.737 [10] and TR 28.808 [11].

Release 17, which meant the starting point of the normative phase of NTN in 3GPP, focused on optimizing power consumption for devices operating within the NTN framework. Such optimization was particularly crucial for Internet of Things (IoT) applications, where power efficiency is a vital consideration. Additionally, Release 17 [12] delved into enhancing coverage and connectivity in remote and underserved areas, leveraging the inherent strengths of NTNs.

Looking ahead, the integration of NTNs into 5G and beyond is expected to continue evolving. The upcoming Release 18 includes work items to enhance NT and NB-IoT/eMTC over NTN. Structurally, different working groups are working to adopt and integrate design aspects of NTNs, especially in the Radio Access Network (RAN), Service and System Aspects (SA), to Core Network and Terminals (CT) working groups. Besides that, future releases will also focus on enhancing the performance of NTNs, addressing challenges like latency, reliability, and throughput to make them more viable for a broader range of applications.

2.2. 3GPP Non-Terrestrial Networks Architectures

Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) are communication architectures that incorporate satellites, high-altitude platforms, or other spacecraft to support and extend in terms of coverage terrestrial telecommunications networks. NTNs aim to provide robust, wide-area connectivity, especially in remote or underserved regions, ensuring seamless integration with ground-based infrastructure. They are a new element introduced in the 5G architecture designed to offer resilience and coverage advantages over solely terrestrial systems.

NTNs main architectural components include [7]:

- 5G Core (5GC): This is the backbone of the 5G network, which provides the main control and processing functions necessary to manage the network's operations, including user data processing, mobility management, authentication, and access to network services.
- Next-Generation NodeB (gNB): This element represents the base stations in 5G networks, which connect directly to the user equipment (UE) over the radio interface, referred to as the Uu interface. The gNB is responsible for all radio-related functions.
- Ground Station (GS): The gateway serves as a bridge between the terrestrial 5G network and the NTN payload. It is responsible for the feeder link, which involves uplinking and downlinking communications to the NTN payload.
- NTN Payload: This is the satellite component that carries the payload. As detailed in the sequel, the payload can be transparent or regenerative. As for the transparent payload, it receives signals from the gateway via the feeder link, amplifies them, and retransmits them to the user equipment (UE) through the service link, and vice versa. The NTN payload operates in a 'bent-pipe' manner, meaning it does not process the content of the signals but simply relays them between the GS and the user terminals. Conversely, in the regenerative payload case, the payload transforms and amplifies an uplink RF signal before transmitting it on the downlink, where transformation may include demodulation, decoding, re-encoding, re-modulation and/or filtering.
- User Equipment (UE): These are the end-user devices, such as smartphones, tablets, or other types of terminals, that communicate with the network. In an NTN scenario, the UE receives and transmits signals to and from the NTN payload via the service link.

Figure 2 from [7] presents the different network architecture supported by the transparent (Figure 2.a) and regenerative payloads (Figure 2.b and Figure 2.c). The transparent payload-based architecture has been the primary specification defined by 3GPP in Releases 17 and 18. Instead, the specification of regenerative payload-based architecture, where either full gNB (Figure 2.b) or only gNB-DU (Figure 2.c) are implemented on board the satellite, has been left for beyond Release 18.

(a) RAN architecture with transparent payload

(b) RAN architecture with regenerative satellite and gNB processed payload

(c) RAN architecture with a regenerative satellite based on gNB-DU

Figure 2. Satellite based NG-RAN architectures

As overviewed in Figure 2, two different architectures are proposed based on the payload of the satellite.

Transparent Payload

Transparent payload architectures in Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) represent a foundational approach to satellite communication systems, which, despite their simplicity, play a significant role in today's global communication infrastructure. In a transparent payload architecture, the satellite functions primarily as a relay station in space, facilitating the transmission of signals between ground stations and user terminals without altering or processing the content of the data. This straightforward approach has its roots in the earliest days of satellite communications and continues to be widely used across various types of satellite systems.

The main function of a transparent payload is to receive signals from an Earth-based transmitter, amplify and reconstruct these signals, and then retransmit them back to Earth or to another satellite in the constellation. This process involves the use of transponders, which are responsible for the reception, amplification, and retransmission of signals at specific frequencies. The inexistence of onboard processing entails that transparent payloads do not demodulate, decode, re-encode, or remodulate the signals.

Instead, they act as a "bent-pipe," simply reflecting signals back to Earth or to the next relay point in space.

Implementing transparent payload architectures in NTN offers several advantages, making them an attractive option for many applications. However, there are also limitations to transparent payload architectures. Both advantages and limitations are included in Table 1.

Table 1. Advantages and limitations of Transparent Payload architectures

Concept	Description
Advantages	
Simplicity and Reliability	Without the need for complex onboard processing, transparent payloads are simpler and can be more reliable over time. This simplicity also translates to a lower likelihood of operational failures
Cost-Effectiveness	The reduced complexity of transparent payloads compared to regenerative payloads can significantly lower the cost of satellite design, manufacturing, and operation. This makes them particularly appealing for commercial satellite operators seeking to deploy cost-effective solutions
Latency	For applications where the primary requirement is the direct transmission of signals without processing, transparent payloads can offer reduced latency. The signal travels directly between the ground station and the user terminal without the delays associated with onboard processing.
Versatility	Transparent payloads are versatile and can support a wide range of frequencies and applications, from television broadcasting to internet services. This versatility makes them a staple in both commercial and governmental satellite operations.
Limitations	
Limited Signal Quality Improvement	Unlike regenerative payloads, transparent payloads cannot process signals to correct errors or enhance signal quality. This means that any signal degradation that occurs during transmission cannot be mitigated by the satellite.
Bandwidth Efficiency	Transparent payloads may not optimize bandwidth as efficiently as regenerative payloads, which can adapt compression algorithms and modulation schemes to improve bandwidth utilization.
Network Flexibility and Security	Transparent payloads offer less flexibility in network management and cannot provide onboard encryption or decryption of signals, which limits their use in applications requiring high security or complex network architectures.

No Inter-satellite communications	Transparent payload-based satellites cannot establish inter-satellite communications, thus forcing the user equipment and the ground station to be under the coverage of the same satellite.
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Regenerative Payload

The regenerative payload architecture in NTN proposes a significant advancement in the field of satellite communication systems. Unlike traditional bent-pipe (transparent payload) architectures, where the satellite merely acts as a relay, reflecting signals from the ground station to the user terminal without any processing, regenerative payloads can process the received signals before retransmitting them. This includes the main base station functionalities that include demodulating, decoding, re-encoding, remodulating, and amplifying the signals onboard.

Implementing regenerative payload architecture in NTN in turn, is not trivial and comes with its set of challenges. The complexity of onboard processing requires more advanced and robust satellite payloads, which increases the cost and complexity of satellite design and manufacturing.

Another factor is power consumption. Processing the signal requires higher power capabilities. This impacts the satellite's design, operational lifespan and risks. Furthermore, ensuring the flexibility and scalability of the onboard processing systems to adapt to evolving technologies and standards over time is a considerable challenge.

Following the 3GPP functional splitting rationale consisting in dividing the gNB into two logical nodes, namely gNB-CU implementing upper layers functionalities and gNB-DU implementing lower layers functionalities [13], the regenerative payload architecture also considers the possibility of dividing the gNB into two logical nodes, the gNB-DU embarked on the satellite and the gNB-CU on the ground segment. With this, the complexity of the satellite payload and the requirements in terms of computational capacity and energy consumption are partially compensated.

As a summary, advantages and limitations of the regenerative-based architecture are included in Table 2.

Table 2. Advantages and limitations of Regenerative Payload architectures

Concept	Description
Advantages	
Improved Signal Quality	By processing signals onboard, regenerative payloads can correct errors and regenerate a cleaner signal before retransmission. This significantly enhances the signal quality and reduces the bit error rate, leading to more reliable communication links
Bandwidth Efficiency	Regenerative payloads enable more efficient use of bandwidth. They can employ more advanced and variable compression algorithms, as well as adapt modulation and coding schemes based on the current link conditions. This adaptability optimizes the use of available bandwidth and improves the overall system capacity.

Network Flexibility	With the ability to process signals onboard, regenerative satellites can support more complex network architectures and services. This includes dynamic routing of traffic based on congestion, link quality, or other criteria, enhancing network flexibility and responsiveness to changing conditions.
Enhanced Security	Regenerative payloads can provide onboard encryption and decryption of data, offering an additional layer of security that is particularly beneficial in military or sensitive applications.
Edge computing capabilities	For certain applications, processing data onboard and making routing decisions directly from the satellite can reduce the latency compared to sending data to a ground station for processing.
Limitations	
Payload Complexity	Compared to transparent architectures, regenerative processes require more sophisticated payloads and extensive onboard processing. The implementation of either the full gNB onboard or only the gNB-DU impacts on the complexity.
Higher Cost	The added complexity of the payload impacts on the cost of the satellite, which is significantly higher than the cost of the transparent payload-based satellite. The implementation of either the full gNB on-board or only the gNB-DU impacts on the complexity.
Energy Requirements	Given the additional complexity of regenerative payload-based satellites, the energy requirements are increased when compared with the transparent payload requirements.

2.3. Literature Review

Section written as a literature overview. The section is divided into two subsections: one for Research projects (particularly those funded by EU) and one for literature.

Relevant research projects

The importance of satellite communications in the framework of 5G/B5G has been gaining momentum since the beginning of the works conducted by 3GPP in Release 15 mainly driven by the definition of new use cases and extended requirements for which satellite communications technologies provide feasible solutions. In this context, the role satellite communications are expected to play has led to the creation of consortia and the funding of research initiatives and projects either focused on the study and analysis of satellites to deliver telecommunications services or including satellite communications as a part of a whole multi-layered network architecture.

Although the fixed location of GEO satellites over the vertical of the earth makes these orbits appealing for the deployment of communications constellations, the nuisances derived from their significant height (e.g increased latency and cost) have shift the focus from GEO orbits to lower orbits, namely LEO, thus becoming the core of international

research projects. In a second step, funded projects have delved into the integration of TN and NTN, which is envisaged to be included in Release 19 of 3GPP.

Initiated back in 2015 and finalized in 2017, VITAL (Virtualized hybrid satellite-Terrestrial systems for resilient and flexible future networks) [14] is a UE-funded project aimed at leveraging Network Function Virtualization and Software-Defined-Networking technologies to enable the creation of a unified control plane able to manage terrestrial-satellite hybrid networks. The three main applications addressed within the project are the satellite virtual network operator services; the satellite backhauling; and hybrid telecom services delivery.

5GCHAMPION (5G Communication with a Heterogeneous, Agile Mobile network in the Pyunchang winter Olympic completion) [15] is a joint EU and South Korean Ministry of Science, ICT and Future Planning funded project carried out between 2016 and 2018 with the objective of developing a proof-of-concept able to deliver 5G based communications within the framework of 2018 South Korean Winter Olympics, in which the satellite segment was a substantial part of the Radio Access Network. As a follow-up, 5G-ALLSTAR (5G Agile and flexible integration of Satellite And cellular) [16] was a EU funded project finalized in 2021, which was aimed at researching and developing communications technologies able to pave the path towards the integration and interworking between cellular terrestrial networks and non-terrestrial networks in a multi-access technology. The vision, scope and goals of the project can be found in deliverable D2.1 of the project [17].

In parallel, the project SaT5G (Satellite and Terrestrial Network for 5G) [18] aimed at leveraging SDN and NFV technologies to enable the integration of 5G terrestrial and satellite networks by dividing the project goals into six pillars. That is, implementation of 5G SDN and NFV satellite networks; development of an integrated network management and orchestration; design multi-link and heterogeneous transport; development of the harmonisation of satellite communications with the 5G control and user planes; extension of 5G security into satellite communications; and development of caching and multicast technologies to provide optimised content and NFV distribution.

DYNASAT (Dynamic Spectrum Sharing and Bandwidth-Efficient Techniques for High-Throughput MIMO Satellite Systems) [19], which commenced in December 2020 and finalized in March 2023, investigated novel bandwidth efficient transmission technologies specifically designed for 5G NGSO radio access network infrastructure, including MIMO, dynamic spectrum access techniques, frequency reuse schemes, clustering of end-users, coordinated multipoint transmissions and interference mitigation techniques, among others. Interestingly, the project defined two subsets of KPIs indicators and targets, divided into economical KPIs and Technical KPIs [20]. From the economic side, they are summarized as system CAPEX, OPEX, TCO, revenues and interest rate of return. On the other hand, technical KPIs included Performance with single radio link, experienced data rate, frequency re-use factor, spectral efficiency, etc. Further details can be found in Tables 6 and 7 in [20].

Leveraging the communications capabilities of satellites by applying novel AI/ML techniques, the ATRIA (AI-Powered Ground Segment Control for Flexible Payloads) [21] project proposes the creation of a generic and intelligent tool designed to obtain the optimal flexible payload configuration given the available satellite resources and to meet on-demand the requirements of requested services.

Also, in an effort to move forward towards 6G NTN, project TRANTOR (5G+ evoluTion to mutioRbitAI multibaNd neTwORks in the definition of NTNs and their integration with TN) [22] aims to validate the satellite value chain in orbit, including a converged radio access network and automated resource management across various bands, satellites, and orbits. TRANTOR specifically aims to develop innovative solutions for managing satellite networks at the ground segment. These solutions are fully integrated into the 3GPP management framework and enable significant scaling up of diverse satellite traffic demands and capacities in a highly dynamic, cost-effective, band- and orbit-agnostic manner. In order to effectively and reliably fulfil the needs of satellite clients, real-time radio resource management across different satellite systems is made possible by AI governance. This project includes the implementation of six different demonstrations, namely 1) End-to-End single band connectivity with a single GEO satellite; 2) End-to-End single band connectivity with a single drone-emulated LEO satellite; 3) End-to-End single band connectivity with CU/DU split with OBP satellite; 4) Multi-band transmission from a single GEO satellite; 5) Multi-satellite, multi-band transmission using two GEO satellites; and 6) Multiorbital, multi-band transmission using a GEO and a drone-emulated LEO satellites.

Similarly, the 5G-STARDUST (Satellite and Terrestrial Access for Distributed, Ubiquitous, and Smart Telecommunications) project [23] proposes a fully integrated 5G NTN autonomous system utilising a cutting-edge self-adapting end-to-end connectivity approach to facilitate universal radio access. The principles governing the system design in 5G-STARDUST are 1) highly flexible multi-constellation (multi-orbit) architectures integrated with 5G terrestrial segments; 2) fully 5G-compliant regenerative satellite communications capabilities; 3) unified radio interfaces; 4) data driven AI-based techniques for multi-connectivity and radio resource management tasks; and 5) 3GPP and O-RAN architecture and concepts. As part of the 5G-STARDUST project, scenarios, use cases and services are analysed in [24], along with 5 different deployments including GEO, non-GEO or HAPS, and each use case is matched with an architecture [25].

ETHER (sElf-evolving terrestrial/non-Terrestrial Hybrid nEtwoRks) project [26] proposes an integrated hybrid network consisting of both the terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks, thus developing a unified radio access network able to meet service requirements in the order of complete coverage, improved energy efficiency, 99.99% service continuity and 99.99% reliability, and a reduction in the total cost of ownership. In order to enable these objectives, ETHER project focuses on a set of enabling technologies, such as 1) UE antenna design and implementation; 2) a robust unified waveform, 3) energy-efficient seamless horizontal and vertical handover policies, 4) a zero-touch management and network orchestrator, 5) a flexible payload system, 6) joint communication, compute and storage resource allocation solutions; and 7) energy-efficient semantics-aware information handling techniques combined with edge computing and caching for reduced latency across the distributed 3D compute and storage continuum. The assessment of the proposed hybrid network is defined in 3 specific use cases, defined as 1) flexible payload-enabled service provisioning to semantics-aware and delay-tolerant IoT applications; 2) unified RAN for direct handheld device Access at the Ka-band; and 3) architecture demonstration for air space safety critical operations. These use cases are further described in Section 3.

Similarly to projects described above, UNITE (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles for Non-Terrestrial Communications and Sensing) [27] addresses similar non-terrestrial networks

challenges, although by combining both satellites and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) as the envisioned 6G non-terrestrial architecture segment.

One of the most relevant research EU-funded projects devoted to NTN in the context of 6G communications is 6G-NTN (6G Non-Terrestrial Networks) [28], launched in January 2023 and to be finalized in December 2025. The project is aimed at proposing enablers for full and seamless integration of terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks from a multi-fold perspective covering technical, business, regulatory and standardization aspects. 6G-NTN is intended to extend coverage, resilience, and sustainability of 6G communications by proposing a 3D multi-layered architecture composed of GSOs, NGSOs, HAPS and drones [29]. It describes a set of 10 targeted verticals (consumer; automotive; public safety & defense; utilities/energy/IoT; media and entertainment; railways transportation; maritime transportation; aeronautics; and road transportation/smart cities) and 7 use cases adapted to these targeted verticals (maritime coverage; autonomous using drones; urban air mobility; adaptation to temporary events; connectivity and positioning in remote areas; bi-directional data streams in high mobility; direct communications over satellites) [30], as well as the services requirements for the considered use cases [31][32]. These use cases are further described in Section 3.

Besides projects specifically addressing NTNs and their integration with TNs, projects such as 6G-SANDBOX (Supporting Architectural and technological Network evolutions through an intelligent, secured and twinning enabled Open eXperimentation facility) [33] and ADROIT6G (Distributed Artificial Intelligence-driven open and programmable architecture for 6G networks) [34] include the non-terrestrial segment as a key part of the network architecture. In particular, 6G-SANDBOX is a trial network composed of infrastructures distributed in 4 locations within the EU and offered to third parties for automated experimentation capabilities. These infrastructures include the NTN segment. As for ADROIT6G, it proposes the implementation of a Proof-of-Concept mainly focused on the service of industrial IoT through NTNs.

Relevant research papers

As stated in the previous sections, the extension of 5G/B5G access networks by encompassing both terrestrial and non-terrestrial segments have attracted the interest of the research community over the last years, mainly driven by the challenges posed by 5G and the expected 6G requirements, and the roadmap defined by 3GPP, which defines three stages for interaction between TNs and NTNs: interworking; integration; and unification.

As NTNs have been put on the spotlight due to the potential ability to provide ubiquitous, continuous, and reliable service, the research community has published a plethora of surveying works on NTNs [35], [1], [36], [37], [38], showing the maturity of the ongoing research. For instance, [39] overviews existing technologies, standards and open challenges in the field of satellite IoT, whereas [36] discusses the evolution of NTN paying special attention to the transition between 5G NTNs and 6G NTNs. Similarly to [36] but from a more general perspective, [37] surveys the transition from 5G to 6G, pointing out the challenging integration of TN and NTN.

In [1], new constellation types, on-board processing capabilities, non-terrestrial networks, and space-based data collection/processing are identified as some of the primary drivers of NTN evolution. In terms of applications, the survey outlines the most promising applications, which are i) Earth observation, ii) 5G integration, iii) space

communications, iv) tracking and v) communication for aircraft, marine and aviation. In the same vein, [38] identifies the main challenges in the path towards 6G, that can be summarized as Orbital Edge Computing, End-to-End Routing, Network Slicing, and Network Orchestration. The orbital edge computing concept lies in the possibility of mimicking for satellite networks the edge computing concept already defined for terrestrial networks. However, putting orbital edge computing into practice presents a number of technical difficulties due to the dispersed and mobile nature of satellite networks, which in turn are translated into routing, congestion/flow control, and energy consumption. As for end-to-end routing, the variability of the topology of the spaceborne segment of the network imposes new challenges. Finally, network slicing and network orchestration will face the need to allocate resources in a highly distributed network architecture.

According to [40], the main requirements for TN and NTN integration are the following:

- The integrated TN-NTN must be able to support a wide variety of services.
- The service coverage shall be seamless.
- The integrated network must have integrated network management.
- Reliable security.

On the other hand, the key enablers for integration are summarized as follows:

- The softwarization of the network, and particularly the implementation of SDN/NFV in satellite networks.
- Cognitive radios in satellite networks.
- IoT applications based on satellite communications.
- New communications satellites, such as high throughput satellites or nanosatellites.

Focusing still on the enablers of TN and NTN integration, AI emerges as a cornerstone for network orchestration and optimisation in future 6G unified networks, and the authors of [41] identify possible applications of AI in NTNs. In particular, and according to the authors, AI algorithms will be leveraged to optimise the communication between satellites, gateways, and user equipment.

The existing literature has investigated 5G/B5G NTN architectures based on 3GPP definitions and the performance of each architecture. In [42] and [43], the authors describe the multi-layered architecture of a NTN, consisting of GEO and LEO satellites, along with HAPs deployed at lower altitudes. The work analyses which configuration can provide higher capacity, considering the following configurations: i) single GEO; ii) GEO and LEO; iii) GEO and HAP; and iv) a complete multi-layer configuration with GEO, LEO and HAP. The conclusions drawn by the authors claim that the optimal configuration to maximize the capacity of the NTN consists of a HAP to cover high demand areas and a GEO satellite to provide broader coverage and backhauling capabilities to HAPs.

Yet, the architecture of the NTN is not limited to the spaceborne nodes, and it also embraces the ground station. Aligned with both 3GPP and O-RAN Alliance, the work [44] discusses the implementation of NTN with the O-RAN architecture. The flexibility and the implementation of AI-based control loops of O-RAN confers potential intelligence to future NTNs, but it also poses some challenges. For instance, the work discusses how O-RAN logical interfaces requirements hurdle the actual implementations of NTNs based on O-RAN. For instance, F1 is the interface defined in O-RAN between CU and DU. This interface must be reliable and cannot be implemented over intermittent links, which is

one of the main drawbacks of feeder links in architectures based on LEO. However, the limited coverage and visibility of earth gateways, along with LEO satellites high mobility, impedes this continuity, thus requiring the implementation of Inter-Satellite Links (ISL) and an entity able to manage the routing. In the case of O-RAN, this entity is the near-Real Time Radio Intelligent Controller (near-RT RIC).

The problem of feeder link intermittent connectivity in LEO based scenarios due to satellite mobility has been addressed by 3GPP with the definition of two feeder link switch-over modalities, namely the hard procedure and the soft procedure. In [45], the authors discuss and analyse the performance of the two modalities through simulation. It is apparent that hard feeder link switch-over modality in transparent payload satellite architectures outperforms the soft procedure. In that sense, although 3GPP defined two different architectures (i.e. transparent and regenerative payload), in practice, in the normative phase, regenerative architecture is not considered [46]. This fact is particularly important in scenarios composed of LEO satellites due to the discontinuity of feeder link. Given the delay tolerance of some NB-IoT and mMTC services, regenerative architecture is gaining importance for Store and Forward approaches. The paper sheds light on architecture and procedures adaptations to overcome challenges of discontinuous feeder link operations in regenerative architecture. Also [47] discusses the existing feeder link switch-over procedure, and the exploitation of inter-satellite links to forward data among satellites creating, for instance, a spaceborne mesh network.

In a similar way, in [48] a cooperative architecture is proposed. This architecture is designed to exploit the cooperation between different architecture layers, thus boosting the network capacity and the coverage extension. Finally, [49] introduces the envisioned DetNet-enabled NTN architecture and explains the interplay of the bandwidth potential, computational power, and latency features of different NTN architecture options.

Beyond the technical aspects of NTN, the deployment of satellites involves different aspects and constraints, such as the economic perspective. Thus, in [50], the authors analyse a LEO mega-constellation from a techno-economic perspective, and calculate the cost versus the performance, deriving the cost per bit.

The range of services supported either by NTN or by the integration of TN and NTN has been studied in the literature, identifying mostly IoT services [51], [52], multicast/broadcast services (MBS) [53], [54] and, sporadically, holographic services [55].

Specifically, [51] presents an interesting analysis on the performance of NB-IoT over NTNs composed of a GEO satellite, pointing out the necessary adaptation of NB-IoT mechanisms required to be supported over NTNs. In that sense, results show that, although NB-IoT fits the requirements of 5G NTNs after a convenient adaptation, the performance is degraded in terms of latency and a trade-off between repetitions and retransmissions arises. Instead, in [52], the capacity of a single LEO satellite located at 600km or at 1,200km to serve LTE-M is studied. Results show that a LEO satellite can provide service to 364 users/km² and 78 users/km² at 600km or 1,200km, respectively.

Also, the ability to support multicast/broadcast services (MBS) by NTNs has been analysed in the literature. [53] discusses about the appropriateness of NTN for the provision of MBS in the context of 6G. Although the challenges derived from the specific characteristic of satellite communications (i.e. channel, orbit, mobility, etc.) hinder the service of MBS over NTNs, enablers such as network slicing, network softwarization and AI-enforced decision making are key building blocks to support MBS. The presented results demonstrate that integrating TN and NTNs, along with the exploitation of

unicast/multicast capabilities, can efficiently allocate network resources. Another example can be found in [54], where a novel radio resource management scheme, named Single-Frequency Multi-Beam Transmission (SF-MBT), for efficient delivery of the enhanced Mobile Broadband(eMBB) services over the 5G NR multi-beam NTN systems. In this work, the multiple beams of the satellite are grouped into beam overlapped and non-overlapped areas, outperforming frequency re-use approaches.

Finally, in [55], it is shown that 6G NTNs will be able to support holographic services, that can have QoS requirements of around 2.06 Gbps at 30 frames/s, and up to 100 Gbps-1Tbps with additional sensors of higher resolution and frame rates. For holographic services, it is noted that there are strict requirements in terms of data processing, latency, and stream synchronization.

State-of-the-Art Summary

As shown in the previous subsections, NTN have been gaining momentum over the last years, and this has been translated into a plethora of funded research projects mainly focused on the evaluation and evolution of 5G/B5G based NTNs. Based on the analysis of the ongoing and closed projects described earlier, different services have been considered in the set of use cases of interest. In particular, mMTC and eMBB services have attracted the interest of the research consortia and, to a lesser extent, URLLC services. In the same vein, the operation of satellites as a backhaul for terrestrial networks has been also investigated.

As for the considered architectures, in general multi-layered architectures including GEO and LEO satellites with both transparent and regenerative payloads are assumed. However, flexible payloads that leverage AI enabled technologies are seen as promising solutions. The following table summarizes the services and architecture proposed in the described projects.

Table 3. Summary of scenarios/services and architectures considered in the most relevant projects on 5G/B5G NTN.

Project	Scenarios/services	Architecture
VITAL		Virtualised satellite network
5GCHAMPION	NB-IoT and voice	- LEO, GEO and HAPS - Transparent and regenerative payloads
5G ALLSTAR	Internet Access, VoIP, Video conferencing	- LEO, GEO - Transparent and regenerative
SaT5G	eMBB and backhauling	- LEO, GEO Transparent and regenerative
DYNASAT	Broadcast/multicast; coverage extension; maritime coverage	- LEO - Transparent

ATRIA		- KONNECT VHTS - Flexible payload
TRANTOR	IoT and data	- LEO, GEO - Transparent and regenerative
5G-STARDUST	Residential broadband, backhauling, vehicular communications, PPDR	- LEO, GEO - Regenerative
ETHER	IoT and data	- Flexible payload
6G-NTN	Voice, message, data, video, location service	- Multi-layered LEO, GEO, HAPS and drones - Regenerative

When it comes to the surveyed literature, the main traffic categories are analyzed. Also, the capacity of single satellites or constellations are evaluated without a specific traffic definition, by using full-buffer traffic models. Table 4 summarizes the considered services.

Table 4. Summary of Services considered in the works overviewed in the literature. eMBB includes multicast/broadcast; mMTC includes NB-IoT and mMTC; URLLC includes PPDR.

Service	Works
eMBB	[1], [47], [53], [54]
mMTC	[1], [46], [51], [52]
URLLC	[1], [38], [55]
Unspecified	[42], [43], [44], [45], [48], [50]

Also, different architectures are analyzed in the literature, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Summary of Architectures considered in the works overviewed in the literature.

Work	Multi-layered	Single Layer	GEO	LEO	HAPS	Transparent	Regenerative
[38]	X	X	X	X			
[42]	X		X	X	X		X
[43]	X		X	X	X		X
[44]		X		X			X
[45]		X		X		X	
[46]		X		X			

[47]		X		X			X
[48]	X		X	X	X	X	X
[50]		X		X		X	
[51]		X	X			X	
[52]		X		X		X	
[53]	X		X	X	X	X	X
[54]		X	X			X	
[55]	X		X	X	X		X

3. Use Cases for NTN

The 3GPP undertook a comprehensive study on future-generation access technologies, encompassing a wide range of applications from indoor hotspots to satellite-based enhancements of the 5G system, as outlined in [56]. The integration of satellite communications is not a novel concept within the existing framework, as evident in the operational satellite constellations. In terms of wireless communication, services can be categorized into Broadcast Satellite Services (BSS) such as the commonly known satellite TV, Fixed Satellite Services (FSS) where stationary user equipment (e.g., a VSAT) connects to a satellite for internet, and Mobile Satellite Services (MSS) which parallel the use cases of terrestrial Radio Access Technologies (RAT), as shown in Figure 3 [57]:

Broadcast Satellite Services (BSS), at their essence, might remind one of conventional satellite television broadcasting, like DVB-S2. However, with 5G NTN, these systems can broadcast information not just broadly but also to specific user equipment or groups. This capability is particularly useful for applications such as software updates or targeted information delivery. Another viable business approach involves offloading traffic, particularly when it's relevant to a wide user base, enhancing overall system efficiency.

Fixed Satellite Services (FSS) provide internet access to stationary user equipment, such as VSATs. This service aligns closely with the goals of traditional fixed-line connectivity, offering the advantage of extensive coverage and the ability to serve remote or underserved areas. FSS forms the core business model for certain exclusive constellation systems, including SpaceX's Starlink. Future FSS deployments might introduce mobility, such as systems mounted on vehicles or airplanes. A component of FSS could also include the potential future use of Integrated Access and Backhaul (IAB) or as backhaul for terrestrial 5G networks.

Mobile Satellite Services (MSS) offer services akin to those found in legacy terrestrial networks but with the added benefit of broader coverage areas, enabling ubiquitous connectivity. It's important to recognize that NTN services are complementary to terrestrial 5G systems; while they may not match terrestrial data rates, their focus is on providing global connectivity and fundamental services over vast areas rather than high data rates for individual users. In terms of MSS, it's assumed that handheld user equipment is used outdoors with maximum velocities of 500 km/h for ground-based (train or ship) and up to 1200 km/h for aircraft-mounted VSAT-type terminals.

Figure 3. Examples of NTN use cases described in [57]

According to [58], the current landscape shows that 95% of the global population is now living within the footprint of a mobile broadband network. However, the broadband coverage has remained relatively unchanged during the last years, showing that the remaining uncovered areas are predominantly rural, poor and sparsely populated, thus posing a challenge to reach them. This disparity underscores the primary incentive for employing Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) services: to achieve widespread, uninterrupted connectivity.

The 3GPP's scope extends beyond merely enhancing coverage in underserved regions. Broadly, it defines in [9] three categories of use cases for satellite access in 5G that are listed below:

Service Continuity: This aims to extend Radio Access Technology (RAT) coverage to areas where terrestrial networks are impractical, such as maritime or remote regions. The goal is to ensure seamless service transition between terrestrial 5G and satellite networks, either under a single operator or through collaborative agreements.

Service Ubiquity: With a focus on mission-critical communications, this objective is about maintaining constant system availability, crucial during emergencies like natural disasters that disrupt terrestrial networks. Using NTN links, systems can quickly recover, aligning with public protection and disaster relief (PPDR) goals.

Service Scalability: This involves optimizing traffic management. By shifting traffic from terrestrial to non-terrestrial networks, system efficiency improves, benefiting from NTN's broader coverage.

These three categories are further detailed in [9] with the definition of 12 use cases, each one with the identification of potential requirements [9]:

1. **Roaming between terrestrial and satellite networks:** This use case states the need for tracking and tracing of containers for maritime transportation.
2. **Broadcast and multicast with a satellite overlay:** Extending the features specified in Release 14 for the delivery of television services, this use case defines the need to provide any form of digital content that would need to be distributed towards several UEs taking into account the benefits of the large geographical coverage of satellite networks, with a stand-alone receive only mode, or as a complement to a two-way mode of operation.
3. **Internet of Things with a satellite network:** Provision of extended geographic coverage by delivering services to IoT customers thanks to 5G satellite access and alternative mobile networks access. Specifically, the use case considers coverage extension to terrestrial networks, and provision of roaming to 5G terrestrial networks.
4. **Temporary use of a satellite component:** Use case aimed at analyzing the ability to provide 5G satellite access in the event of disruption of the 5G terrestrial access due to emergency.
5. **Optimal routing or steering over a satellite:** In geographical areas with 5G terrestrial and non-terrestrial access coverage, data is transmitted/received over satellite or terrestrial access network based on service requirements, such as latency.
6. **Satellite transborder service continuity:** Satellite access networks providing coverage across a border where multiple terrestrial networks also provide access, the satellite segment can extend the coverage of terrestrial networks; provide connection to the core of terrestrial networks; and operate as a stand-alone 5G network.
7. **Global satellite overlay:** user equipment accesses the network through a constellation of LEO satellites equipped with a gNB onboard. Satellites are interconnected via intersatellite links creating a mesh access network with improved latency performance or specific end to end security.
8. **Indirect connection through a 5G satellite access network:** To guarantee service continuity in geographical areas without 5G terrestrial connectivity, user equipment without satellite access can be interconnected with a satellite enabled user equipment playing the role of relay node.
9. **5G Fixed Backhaul between NR and the 5G Core:** In this use case, the 5G satellite access is aimed at providing wideband backhaul connection to 5G terrestrial access networks in sparsely populated areas, where fixed terrestrial wideband connectivity (e.g. DSL) is limited by technical or economic reasons.
10. **5G Moving Platform Backhaul:** The use case describes a scenario where 5G satellites provide backhaul connectivity (mainly in the downlink) to trains

equipped with 5G base stations in geographic areas with limited terrestrial coverage.

11. **5G to Premises:** The use case describes a scenario where 5G satellite access network is aimed at providing coverage to residential areas with limited bandwidth connectivity due to their geographical characteristics of the area.
12. **Satellite connection of remote service centre to off-shore wind farm:** The wind power plant communication network at an off-shore wind farm connects to the on-shore and inland remote service centre via 5G satellite connection.

Additionally, 3GPP explores detailed satellite network applications for 5G, extending beyond the primary use cases. These include [6]:

- **Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB):** Offers broadband to remote areas and supports fixed and mobile cells.
- **Network Resilience and Trunking:** Enhances network reliability, especially in remote or isolated areas, leveraging satellite networks' immunity to terrestrial disruptions.
- **Hybrid and Broadcast Connectivity:** Combines terrestrial 5G with NTN for efficient broadcast services.
- **Wide-area IoT (IoT-NTN):** Expands IoT connectivity through satellite links in underserved regions.
- **Public Safety Authority Services:** Supports widespread emergency communication, including public alerts and responder coordination.
- **Aerial-Based Access Networks:** Addresses unique needs like on-demand hotspots and safety in areas without terrestrial backhaul.
- **Temporary Satellite Connectivity:** Utilized in disaster relief to compensate for terrestrial network failures.
- **High Altitude Platform Station (HAPS) Specific Cases:** Includes quasi-stationary UAV support for services like fixed wireless access and disaster recovery.

Also, in the survey in [1], the authors identify a list of use cases categorized into the three well-known service categories defined by ITU, namely eMBB, mMTC and URLLC. Specifically, the use cases per service category are stated in the following.

Satellite Use Cases for eMBB:

- **Backhauling and tower feed:** In this use case, the satellite is complementary, thus backhauling the traffic or broadcasting popular content to the edge.
- **Trunking and head-end feed:** In remote areas, connectivity is guaranteed by satellite, since terrestrial networks cannot be deployed.
- **Hybrid multiplay:** Satellites, along with terrestrial network, are part of a hybrid network in underserved areas.
- **Communications on the move:** Satellites provide 5G service to moving platforms.

Satellite Use Cases for mMTC:

- **Wide area IoT services:** This use case includes the scenarios in which groups of IoT devices are deployed over a wide area and report information or are

controlled by a central server. Typical applications for this use case range critical surveillance of gas infrastructure, fleet management, or farming.

- **Local area IoT services:** In this use case, IoT devices collect local data and report it to a server, with applications such as advanced metering.

Satellite Use Cases for URLLC: This use case is the most challenging for NTN (as well as for terrestrial networks) due to the strict requirements in terms of availability, maximum delay, and very high reliability. Typical applications range autonomous driving, or factory automation.

The definition of use cases included in 3GPP has been extended and/or particularized in the plethora of international research projects aimed at contributing to the evolution of 5G/B5G satellite networks and their integration with 5G terrestrial networks as a key step to build a 3D multi-layered access network [59]. Recently, some of the most prominent EU-funded projects, such as 6G-NTN [28] and ETHER [26], have incorporated specific use cases in the framework of 5G/B5G NTN. In the following, a list of such use cases is overviewed.

The 6G-NTN project (launched in January 2023 and to be finalized in December 2025) has rooted the analysis of the potential of NTN in the framework of future 6G communications in the definition of 10 verticals and 7 use cases, being a subset or a particularization of the use cases defined by 3GPP [30]. Specifically, the set of use cases is shown below:

- UC1: Maritime Coverage for search and rescue coast guard intervention
- UC2: Autonomous power line inspection using drones
- UC3: Urban air mobility
- UC4: Adaptation to PPDR or Temporary Events
- UC5: Consumer Handheld Connectivity and Positioning in Remote Areas
- UC6: Continuous Bi-directional Data Streams in High Mobility
- UC7: Direct Communication over Satellites.

These use cases are tightly coupled with diverse verticals and can be classified into the three use cases categories identified in [9] and overviewed earlier in this section. Based on this classification, the following table is devised to match verticals, use cases and service categories:

Table 6. Targeted verticals and service category for the proposed use cases, extracted from Table 1 in [30]. In the table, X means that use cases explicitly illustrate the verticals, and O means that use cases can illustrate verticals with minor adaptations.

	UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4	UC 5	UC 6	UC 7
Targeted verticals							
1 Consumer					X		
2 Automotive			O		O	X	X
3 Public Safety & Defense	X		O	X	O		X
4 Utilities / Energy / IoT		X			O		X
5 Media and Entertainment				X			
6 Railways transportation		O	O				O
7 Maritime transportation	X				O		X
8 Aeronautic / drone sector		X	X				O

1	Road transportation / Smart cities			X		O	O	O
0								
Service Category								
1	Service Continuity	X	X	X		X	X	
2	Service Ubiquity	X		X	X	X		X
3	Service Scalability				X			

In a similar vein, the ETHER project [26] has defined the following 3 use-cases:

- UC1: ETHER flexible payload-enabled service provisions to semantics-aware and delay-tolerant IoT applications.
- UC2: ETHER unified RAN for direct handheld device Access at the Ka-band
- UC3: ETHER architecture demonstration for air space safety critical operations

4. Scenarios in 6GSatNet

6GSatNet's objectives are twofold. Initially, the project focuses on assessing the performance of Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) in various connectivity contexts. This includes the exploration and identification of optimal satellite-network architectures that optimize service provision while reducing costs. The analysis will also involve multi-layered NTNs to determine their key performance indicators based on a predefined set of parameters. Subsequently, leveraging the insights from the analysis of NTN capabilities, the project aims to define the suite of services that can be delivered by each network layer.

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Figure 4 Reference architecture for 6GSatNet scenarios. Upper subfigure: transparent payload. Lower subfigure: regenerative payload [60].

The project's reference architecture is illustrated in Figure 4 and Figure 5, depicting both one layer and two-layer Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) that integrate both Geostationary Orbit (GEO) and Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites. These satellites are capable of interconnecting through Inter-Satellite Links (ISL) and establishing connections to ground gateways via the Feeder Link (FL). In the 6GSatNet reference architecture we will consider ISL links enable LEO satellites to support and relay information to GEO satellites. We will not consider scenarios in which GEO satellites serve users directly. The feasibility and availability of ISLs and FLs will be thoroughly evaluated in individual use cases and experiments.

Figure 5. Multi-layered NTN

Within the framework of the reference architecture, the set of parameters that will be analyzed is detailed in the following:

1. Orbit of the satellites (Stationary or Non-Stationary).
2. Constellation type (LEO or GEO).
3. Number of planes of the constellation.
4. Number of satellites per plane.
5. Multi-level constellation.
6. Inter-Satellite Link capacity.
7. Uplink and downlink capacity.
8. Transparent or regenerative payload. In alignment with TR 38.821 [7], for the regenerative payload architecture, either the gNB is embarked on the satellite, or only the gNB-DU is embarked on the satellite, while the gNB-CU is left on the ground.
9. Mobility of users and LEO satellites.
10. Number of users.
11. Heterogeneity in satellite resources

These parameters will be defined for a wide range of evaluation scenarios, considering different satellite architectures, ISL capacities according to the LEO-LEO or LEO-GEO communication model, uplink and downlink capacity, types of gNB architecture (transparent or regenerative), etc... These will depend on the type of application/service we will be addressing, as the mMTC requirements differ from those for eMBB. The following sections define the methodology to address the evaluation as well as present several configurations that will be evaluated.

The evaluation of scenarios based on the reference architecture will be approached from a “Tradespace” perspective [61], where the evaluation and comparison of different options or solutions for each problem, considering multiple factors or dimensions that can be conflicting or even contradictory among them. In accordance with the guidelines provided by 5GPPP in [62] and [63], the KPIs utilized in the analysis of the solutions are: (1) peak data rate, (2) experienced data rate, (3) traffic capacity, (4) mobility, (5) latency, (6) reliability and (7) connectivity density. Services considered in the project are described along with their requirements in Section 6. Also, the approached methodology, namely “tradespace”, is described in Section 6.

5. NTN Technical Requirements

The ITU-R M.2514-0 [60] outlines the vision, requirements, and evaluation guidelines for satellite radio interfaces of IMT-2020, highlighting its crucial role in enhancing global communication by integrating satellite components with terrestrial networks. This integration aims to ensure service continuity and ubiquitous coverage, especially in under-served areas, leveraging satellite's unique capabilities to overcome geographical challenges.

IMT-2020 provides a detailed description of the requirements to support to enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), massive machine-type communications (mMTC), and ultra-reliable and low-latency communications (URLLC), with satellite components specifically addressing eMBB and mMTC scenarios. These include providing high-speed internet in rural and remote areas, supporting connectivity for vehicles and vessels, and facilitating a wide array of machine-to-machine communications. The document recognizes the inherent differences between satellite and terrestrial components, such as latency and data rates, and proposes tailored technical performance requirements for satellite interfaces.

To evaluate proposed satellite radio interfaces, the document outlines test environments, and methodologies, focusing on example scenarios including eMBB and mMTC. These scenarios are complementary to the ones presented in this document. Each scenario addresses specific use cases like high data rate applications in remote areas, connection of many devices over wide areas, and highly reliable communications, respectively. Evaluation criteria include peak data rate, spectral efficiency, latency, connection density, and mobility among others, ensuring that satellite components can meet diverse service and technical requirements.

The document emphasizes the importance of flexible, efficient satellite networks that can interwork seamlessly with terrestrial networks, thereby enhancing the overall reliability and availability of IMT-2020 services. It sets a framework for developing satellite radio interfaces that can adapt to various bandwidths and support different user equipment types, aiming for a harmonious integration within the global IMT-2020 ecosystem.

In what follows we define the Key performance indicators for the eMBB and mMTC scenarios as described by the ITU-R M.2514-0 and that will be considered in this project.

It is important to note that the ITU-R M.2514-0 defines the minimum envisioned requirements for NTNs, regardless of the addressed service. Yet, the actual requirements for eMBB services like voice, data or messaging may differ and even not require or meet the minimum ITU requirements.

5.1 eMBB minimum requirements

The ITU M2410 [64] document presents the definition of the essential minimum technical performance criteria to guide the uniform definition, specification, and assessment of prospective IMT-2020 radio interface technologies (RITs) or sets of such technologies (SRITs). The key minimum requirements for NTN are defined in M.2514-0 and summarized next for each of the targeted services in the project. Taking into account the literature and considering the information available from commercial deployments, the ITU minimum requirements may be higher than those required for certain NTN scenarios, especially for those requiring very limited resources like messaging. Along the document, these (the ITU) requirements will be considered an optimal case, while for certain scenarios a more constrained set of parameters will be considered.

Table 7. 5.1. ITU M2410 [64] eMBB minimum requirements

Minimum technical requirements items	Downlink or uplink	Required value
Peak data rate	Uplink	2 Mbit/s
	Downlink	70 Mbit/s
Peak spectral efficiency	Uplink	1.5 bit/s/Hz
	Downlink	3 bit/s/Hz
User experienced data rate	Uplink	100 kbit/s
	Downlink	1 Mbit/s
5 th percentile user spectral efficiency	Uplink	0.003 bit/s/Hz
	Downlink	0.03 bit/s/Hz
Average spectral efficiency	Uplink	0.1 bit/s/Hz
	Downlink	0.5 bit/s/Hz
Area traffic capacity	Uplink	1.5 kbit/s/km ²
	Downlink	8 kbit/s/km ²
User Plane latency	N/A	10 ms
Control Plane latency	N/A	40 ms
Connection density	N/A	Not specified
Energy efficiency	N/A	None
Reliability	N/A	Not specified
Mobility – UE speed	N/A	250 km/h
Mobility - Traffic channel link data rate	N/A	0.005 bit/s/Hz
Mobility interruption time	N/A	50 ms
Bandwidth	N/A	At least up to and including 30 MHz

5.2 mMTC minimum requirements

For the mMTC service the minimum requirements are presented in the following table:

Table 8. 5.1. ITU M2410 [64] mMTC minimum requirements

Minimum technical requirements items	Downlink or uplink	Required value
Connection density	N/A	500 devices/km ²

6. Tradespace evaluation scenarios

In this section we identify the variables that will be considered in the tradespace analysis and evaluation that will be conducted along the project. We follow the methodology as outlined in [61]. The flowchart of the tradespace exploration-based methodology is outlined in Figure 6:

Figure 6. Flowchart of the tradespace exploration-based evaluation

As shown in the figure, the evaluation consists of different phases that are detailed in the following:

- **Use case requirements:** The set of minimum requirements and optimal requirements are defined for the use case under analysis. The set of requirements is the input for the tradespace exploration, including: Number of users; Connectivity density; Mobility, Uplink/Downlink. The ITU parameters will be considered the optimal configuration, while for certain services, a more constrained requirements will be used.
- **Generations of Constellations:** Generation of constellations taking into account the set of variables: Single/Multi-layer constellation; Constellation type; Number of planes; Number of satellites per plane.
- **Generation of Architectures:** Given a constellation, the network architecture is generated by setting the variables: Payload type (transparent/regenerative); (heterogeneous) satellite resources; Intersatellite Links; Ground Station location.
- **Analysis of Architectures:** Simulation of the generated architecture and collection of Metrics.
- **Calculation of Figure of Merit:** Given the metrics simulated, definition and calculation of the figure-of-merit required to evaluate the generated architectures. Initially, the figure of merit will be based on the figure-of-merit defined in [61]. The definition of different figures-of-merit will be analyzed to find out the most suitable definition.
- **Cost Calculation:** The cost of the architectures will be calculated based on the existing literature, including the cost of the satellites, the cost of launching, and the cost of maintenance.

In particular, we address the Direct-to-handset use case for voice, messaging and data, i.e. the typical cellphone usage scenarios and an IoT connectivity use case, where data collection applications are mainly considered.

UC1-D2H-voice, UC1-D2H-data, UC1-D2H-messaging, and UC2-IoTconnectivity-IoT

The following table identifies the explored scenarios:

Table 9. Description of Usage scenarios and test environments.

	UC1	UC1	UC1	UC2
Usage Scenarios	UC1-D2H-voice	UC1-D2H-data	UC1-D2H-messaging	UC2-IoTconnectivity
Test environment	Offshore-voice	Offshore-data	Offshore-messaging	Offshore-IoT

To better focus the evaluation, we center the use cases in realistic environments. For the sake of experimentation and analysis, we consider direct-to-handset offshore scenarios as well as common IoT scenarios in offshore monitoring applications. Offshore applications are relevant use cases for NTN and studying the network architectures to serve such applications may be a good starting point to understand the value of these services. Despite the fact that we conduct the evaluation with this rationale behind, the results can be extrapolated to other applications and use cases, and the results obtained considering the number of UEs, the covered area and the NTN architecture, etc. may apply to other use cases with analogous settings.

6.1. UC1. Direct-to-handset use case

In UC1, we envision a scenario where Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) are deployed to deliver 5G services to user equipment, encompassing both static devices and mobile terminals. This service delivery falls within the enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) service category, which is designed to provide high-speed data and multimedia services over wide geographical areas. Note, however, that the voice, data and messaging services, when offered via a NTN infrastructure do not need to strictly meet the envisioned minimum requirements for eMBB, first because eMBB does not consider messaging and voice services, but also because these technologies are being evolved and in the current state not all the eMBB requirements can be met (considering existing deployments or the information obtained from the analyzed state of the art).

To achieve this, the scenario explores and evaluates various satellite deployment strategies. These strategies include networks consisting of single Low Earth Orbit (LEO) constellations or a two-layered network combining both LEO and Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO) satellites. A distinctive feature of these deployments is the use of regenerative payloads, which can process data onboard, thus improving the quality of the service by reducing latency and enhancing signal strength. Additionally, the scenario considers high data rate Inter-Satellite Links (ISLs) capable of operating over distances ranging from 1500 to 2500 kilometers. These ISLs are crucial for maintaining a seamless connection between satellites, enabling the network to efficiently relay data across vast distances.

As introduced previously and for the sake of providing a scenario in which specific requirements can be defined, we will focus on offshore scenarios, consider mobile terminals on ships or offshore platforms. In such environments, traditional terrestrial network coverage is often nonexistent or severely limited. The proposed NTN setup, with its dual-layer (LEO and GEO) approach, offers a promising solution to this challenge enabling a wide array of applications:

- Real-time navigation and weather updates, ensuring safer and more efficient maritime operations.
- High-definition video conferencing and streaming services for crew welfare, allowing them to stay connected with families or access entertainment during long voyages.
- Remote monitoring and control of offshore facilities, enhancing operational safety and efficiency by allowing instant data access and decision-making capabilities.

Table 10. Use Case 1 (UC1) summary.

Parameter	Value
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Service	eMBB
Constellation	LEO/ LEO and GEO
Terminals	Static and mobile
Payload	Regenerative
Inter-Satellite Links	If present, high data rate (1-10 Gbps) and distance around 1500-2500 km

Note however, that even if we focus on this specific scenario, the obtained results can be extrapolated to other scenarios with similar specifications in terms of number of users, type of service and NTN setting.

Evaluation Requirements

In this section we present the scenarios that will be explored with the tradespace methodology. Simulations will be conducted for the following scenarios and specific requirements in order to determine the most appropriate architectures to address the use cases. We based the requirements definition in the ITU M2540 document as introduced in the previous section. Yet, these requirements can be considered the ideal since current state of the art and commercial systems do not fully convey with. For the purpose of the evaluation and following the tradespace methodology we will also introduce economic cost constraints, in order to perform the study, not only from a technical perspective but also to open a discussion considering the most suitable architectures from an economical perspective. As the cost of a satellite may vary a lot depending on the used technology and the launching conditions, we cannot use exact estimates, but we believe we can agree that the cost of developing, launching and maintaining a LEO satellite is significantly lower than that of a GEO satellite. With that we will add cost categories for satellites, being low, mid and high depending on the type of deployment and capacity. These categories, may serve latter for a discussion in which constellation costs can also have an influence.

The three considered use cases are voice, data and messaging for an eMBB service.

Table 11. Evaluation requirements for eMBB-voice (UC1).

Offshore-eMBB-v	Scenario v1	Scenario v2	Scenario v3	Scenario v4
Architecture Metrics				
Orbit of the satellites.	Non-Stationary	Non-Stationary	Non-Stationary	Non-Stationary + Stationary
Constellation type.	LEO	LEO	LEO	LEO + GEO
Number of planes of the constellation.	1	1	2	2 + 1
Number of satellites per plane.	20	28	15+10	20 + 10 + 2
Multi-level constellation.	No	No	Yes	Yes

Inter-Satellite Link capacity.	No	No	Yes	Yes
Number of users	500-5.000 users	500-5.000 users	500-5.000 users	500-5.000 users
Transparent or regenerative payload.	Regenerative	Regenerative	Regenerative	Regenerative
Mobility of users.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Elevation Angles (UE)	20-40°	20-40°	20-40°	LEO: 20-40° GEO: 20°
Studied Area	1.000.000 km2	1.000.000 km2	1.000.000 km2	1.000.000 km2
Satellite Costs	20 Low	28 Low	15 Low + 10 Mid	20 Low + 10 Mid + 2 High
Operational Network Requirements				
Peak data rate (UL/DL) (per user)	256kbps/s-256kbps/s	256kbps/s-256kbps/s	256kbps/s-256kbps/s	256kbps/s-256kbps/s
Minimum Experienced data rate (UL/DL)	64kbps	64kbps	64kbps	64kbps
Spectral efficiency (UL/DL)	0.5 bit/s/Hz / 0.1 bit/s/Hz			

Table 12. Evaluation requirements for eMBB-data (UC1).

Offshore-eMBB-d	Scenario d1	Scenario d2	Scenario d3	Scenario d4
Architecture Metrics				
Orbit of the satellites.	Non-Stationary	Non-Stationary	Non-Stationary	Non-Stationary + Stationary
Constellation type.	LEO	LEO	LEO	LEO + GEO
Number of planes of the constellation.	1	1	2	2 + 1
Number of satellites per plane.	20	28	15+10	20 + 10 + 2
Multi-level constellation.	No	No	Yes	Yes
Inter-Satellite Link capacity.	No	No	Yes	Yes
Number of users	500-5.000 users	500-5.000 users	500-5.000 users	500-5.000 users
Transparent or	Regenerative	Regenerative	Regenerative	Regenerative

regenerative payload.				
Mobility of users.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Elevation Angles (UE)	20-40°	20-40°	20-40°	LEO: 20-40° GEO: 20°
Studied Area	1.000.000 km2	1.000.000 km2	1.000.000 km2	1.000.000 km2
Satellite Costs	20 Low	28 Low	15 Low + 10 Mid	20 Low + 10 Mid + 2 High
Operational Network Requirements				
Peak data rate (UL/DL) (per users)	2 Mbits/s - 30 Mbit/s [AST]	2 Mbits/s - 30 Mbit/s	2 Mbits/s - 30 Mbit/s	2 Mbits/s - 30 Mbit/s
Minimum Experienced data rate (UL/DL)	100kbp/s -100kbp/s	100kbp/s	100kbp/s	100kbp/s
Spectral efficiency (UL/DL)	0.5 bit/s/Hz / 0.1 bit/s/Hz			

Table 13. Evaluation requirements for eMBB-messaging (UC1).

Offshore-eMBB-m	Scenario m1	Scenario m2	Scenario m3	Scenario m4
Architecture Metrics				
Orbit of the satellites.	Non-Stationary	Non-Stationary	Stationary	Non-Stationary + Stationary
Constellation type.	LEO	LEO	GEO	LEO + GEO
Number of planes of the constellation.	1	1	1	2 + 1
Number of satellites per plane.	20	28	15+10	20 + 10 + 2
Multi-level constellation.	No	No	No	Yes
Inter-Satellite Link capacity.	No	No	No	Yes
Number of users	500-5.000 users	500-5.000 users	500-5.000 users	500-5.000 users
Transparent or regenerative payload.	Regenerative	Regenerative	Regenerative	Regenerative
Mobility of users.	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Elevation Angles (UE)	20-40°	20-40°	20°	LEO:20-40° GEO: 20°
Studied Area	1.000.000 km2	1.000.000 km2	1.000.000 km2	1.000.000 km2

Satellite Costs	20 Low	28 Low	15 Low + 10 Mid	20 Low + 10 Mid + 2 High
Operational Network Requirements				
Peak data rate (UL/DL) (per users)	256 kbps/s - 256 kbps/s			
Minimum Experienced data rate (UL/DL)	10kbps	10kbps	10kbps	10kbps
Spectral efficiency (UL/DL)	0.5 bit/s/Hz / 0.1 bit/s/Hz			

The tables above provide the requirements that will serve as the base for our evaluation of the Direct-to-handset eMBB use cases. It is important to clarify some of the value presented in the table. First, in the eMBB scenarios we consider there is service continuity. This means that for a studied area (e.g. 10^6 km^2) any UE will be covered by a satellite at any moment, this will be true regardless of we represent an offshore use case. Some of the scenarios consider architectures in which LEO or LEO and GEO satellites have the capability to communicate via ISL. User mobility, in the offshore scenario is considered, despite the relative speed of users with respect to the satellites. As we are considering that for the given area the connectivity service (10^6 km^2) is continuous handovers may occur in a very similar frequency as if we consider users static. We want also to point out that the study will also consider an estimate of the constellation cost. As part of the Tradespace exploration, the Pareto optimal solution may provide the satellite constellation architecture that maximizes the service to the end users while minimizes its cost. Based on the state-of-the-art Tradespace exploration like in [61], we will define a costs estimates for satellites, having a lower cost for LEO satellites than for GEO.

6.2. UC2. IoT connectivity use case

UC2 defines a scenario composed of a sparse LEO constellation with intermittent or full coverage. User terminals are static and request delay-tolerant NB-IoT based services. As detailed in Section 4, the heterogeneity in satellite resources will be analysed. Thus, although in general satellite platforms are resource-constrained and so satellites based on a regenerative gNB-DU architecture are more common, also regenerative payload with full gNB onboard will be considered. LEO satellites may establish low data-rate ISLs among them.

Table 13. Use Case 2 (UC2) summary.

Parameter	Value
Service	NB-IoT (mMTC)
Constellation	Sparse LEO
Terminals	Static
Payload	Regenerative
Inter-Satellite Links	Low data rate (around 10-100 kbps) and distance around 1500 km

As indicated will consider use cases in offshore areas. Future offshore communications are seen to present unsatisfied requirements in terms of direct-handset access, network coverage, data access latency and seem to be addressable by new and novel satellite architectures. The application of these services to recreational, energy, marine transportation, and logistics, among others is becoming increasingly important to facilitate such activities and develop new business opportunities including safety and quality of service. Beyond the further capabilities of NTN will develop novel IoT use cases in remote and uncovered areas. A major potential for IoT are the oceanic sensing and communication applications, for climate, ocean and marine life control, pollution, geotechnical exploration, or marine infrastructure monitoring.

IoT Connectivity Requirements

In this section we propose the tradespace requirements for the IoT use case. It considers the network parameters of the satellites, their operational orbits, and the technological capabilities of their payloads. This analysis is instrumental in supporting the complex decision-making process involved in satellite constellation design, ensuring that the selected architecture not only meets the immediate requirements of IoT connectivity but also aligns with long-term strategic goals. Along the project we will be conducting the tradespace analysis and simulation based on these initial requirements leading to the proper recommendations to address these use cases based on optimized services guarantees and minimized cost.

Table 14. Evaluation requirements for mMTC (UC2).

Offshore-mMTC-i	Scenario i1	Scenario i2	Scenario i3	Scenario i4
Architecture Metrics				
Orbit of the satellites.	Non-Stationary	Non-Stationary	Non-Stationary	Non-Stationary/Stationary
Constellation type.	LEO	LEO	LEO	LEO + GEO
Number of planes of the constellation.	1	1	2	2
Number of satellites per plane.	15	25	15+10	15 + 2
Multi-level constellation.	No	No	Yes	Yes
Inter-Satellite Link capacity.	No	No	Yes	Yes
Connection density	5-500 users/km ²	5-500 users/km ²	5-500 users/km ²	5-500 users/km ²
Transparent or regenerative payload.	Regenerative	Regenerative	Regenerative	Regenerative
Mobility of users.	No	No	No	No

Elevation Angles	20-40°	20-40°	20-40°	LEO:20-40° GEO: 20°
Studied Area	1.000.000 km ²	1.000.000 km ²	1.000.000 km ²	1.000.000 km ²
Satellite Costs	15 Low	25 Low	15 Low + 10 Mid	15 Low + 2 High
Operational Network Requirements				
Peak data rate	10Mbits/s - 2 Mbit/s			
Experienced data rate	20kbp/s - 250kb/s	20kbp/s - 250kb/s	20kbp/s - 250kb/s	20kbp/s - 250kb/s
Spectral efficiency	0.5 bit/s/Hz / 0.1 bit/s/Hz			

6.3 Determining the number of satellites in a constellation for the evaluation

We provide in this section a brief description assessing the full coverage service with the selected number of satellites. We set from the worst case in which LEO satellites are orbiting at 600km, at 7.5km/s and the UEs have a minimum elevation angle in order to reach the satellite of 20°. In this scenario, the orbital period of a satellite is around 97 min. The shortest visibility window, which occurs when the satellite's path is at the maximum allowable distance from the observer's zenith but still reaches a minimum elevation angle of 20°, results in a visibility time of approximately 402.25 seconds, or about 6.7 minutes (corresponding to an arc in the satellite footprint at 20°) if the device is located in the Equator. This represents the minimum duration for which the satellite is visible during a pass where it is furthest from directly overhead.

Figure 7. Satellite footprint illustration

The longest window occurs when the satellite passes over the zenith of the device. In the Equator this window is approximately 804.51 seconds (13.4minutes). In the following

figure we can observe the window duration for the different visibility angles [65] for the Barcelona latitude.

Figure 8. Access duration as a function of the elevation angle in a latitude of 42 degrees (Barcelona)[65]

For a 20° visibility angle we can observe the boxplot, presenting 50% of the passes with a duration between 250s and 320s. If we consider satellites have an overlap of 25% of their footprints, 26 satellites may be sufficient to provide an almost full area coverage in a latitude like Barcelona.

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